

**AN
INTERNSHIP REPORT
ON
DENTAL CLINIC MANAGEMENT SYSTEM PROJECT
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INTRODUCTION

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Dental Clinics, Dental department or other specialty department in a general hospital can use this software. Though this software was designed primarily with the inputs from dental Clinics, it could be adoptable in other specialty hospitals also, with some little changes in the medical terms, database etc.

DCMS software has been developed to provide comprehensive software solution for the clinics. But there are clinics that cannot afford to run such comprehensive system or may not be required due to the volume of work handled. Still to encourage such clinics to use computers for generating useful information to run the organization efficiently, we provide the following Software from which one can choose according to their requirement.

It is a system which will help dentist to keep track patient dental problems, from time to time. This system allow dentist to help patient to improve their awareness and take care about their oral health. The data regarding the patient dental information will help the patient in order to apply for the next treatment and also to be use for the future.

DCMS can analysis the data that had been captured and come out with the analysis report to summarize the dental score for each patient. The reports able to summarize the patient dental healthcare performance from time to time according to the treatment made. Other than help the patient to upgrade their awareness regarding the oral health, these reports will also give benefits to patients as they can view their dental health performance.

EXISTING SYSTEM

Existing system refers to the system that is being followed till now. Presently all the clinics functionalities are done manually. That is if a patient want to consult a doctor he can visit their till his chance called. This is make the person very difficult. An Appointment are distributed directly. The main disadvantage is time consuming. Limitation of existing system is if sum one patient loses his receipt, difficulties to find out patient has assign tickets. To defect this limitation we do computer system.

The current system works as the following:

- In the old system, the user was maintaining the records like number of books, CD's, DVD's and subscribers., Fees Detail and bill (Receipt) in the paper sheets.
- Hence it was very difficult for him to keep track which Customer has been taken which cd or dvd, what is the Bill no, etc.
- The manpower required for this kind of transaction and maintenance of data is higher than the actual requirement.

LIMITATIONS OF EXISTING SYSTEM

No system can be referred as complete system in all aspects. In spite of successful executions of testing plan .The problem arises, when the system is input in the real working environment, the problem that will arise cannot be visualized and their solution cannot be predetermined to be rectified.

- The designed product is stand alone system.
- It works on current basis.
- On-line booking, transaction etc are not possible.
- Lack of security of data.
- Time consuming.
- Consumes large volume of paper work.
- Manual work
- No direct role for the higher officials.
- To avoid all these limitations and make the system working more accurately it needs to be computerized.

PROBLEM DEFINATION

Comprehensive Dental care services that deliver effective, safe, high-quality interventions to those that need them, when and where needed, with minimum waste of resources, and with continuity of care across levels of care, settings, and providers. Our software has the facility to give a unique id for every patient and stores the details of every patient and the Doctor automatically.

PROPOSED SYSTEM:

The DENTAL CLINIC MANAGEMENT SYSTEM software is user-friendly software. The main objectives of the system is which shows and helps you to collect most of the information about Hospitality and Services The system is very simple in design and to implement. The system requires very low system resources and the system will work in almost all configurations.

The main objectives of the proposed system can be enumerated as follows:

1. Patients are easily allocated to the doctors.
2. Doctors Search is possible.
3. Today's patient list help doctors to search their patients

ADVANTAGES OF PROPOSED SYSTEM

The system is very simple in design and to implement. The system requires very low system resources and the system will work in almost all configurations.

1. Security of data.
2. Ensure data accuracy's.
3. Administrator controls the entire system.
4. Reduce the damages of the machines.
5. Minimize manual data entry.
6. Greater efficiency.
7. User friendly and interactive.
8. Minimum time required.

OBJECTIVE AND SCOPE OF THE PROJECT

Our main aim of the project is to get the correct information about particular Patient and to reduce human efforts.

The user can maintain all the records about Patient Details, Appointments, Doctor Details, Follow-ups and Bill and save it in the database. Enable the clinicians and administrators to search documents and records by criteria such as patient name, date of birth, address, and medical condition from within familiar Office applications.

The goals that wish to be achieved are:

1. System manages to save all the patient record accurately and computerized.
2. System able to avoid the data redundancy of patient dental information.
3. System manages to check the available date and time to make appointment between dentist and patient.
4. System able to display patient dental history and treatment that had been done.
5. System provides an interactive tooth illustration charting to make the process of recording patient dental information easier.
6. Generate report of patient dental condition according to the treatment session.
7. Generate statistic report regarding number of patient visit for treatment at the clinic.

ANALYSIS

ANALYSIS:-

It is necessary to analyze the needs and availability before designing any application. This analysis includes study of the existing system and the availability of the resources. The study is conducted on each and every aspect which is necessary to design any enterprise solution.

➤ METHODOLOGY ADOPTED:-

PROCESS MODEL:

In the development of software we have used **Waterfall Model**, the linear sequential mode. This model encompasses the following activities:

a) Analysis Phase:

This refers to the gathering of requirements, with the goal of determining how these requirements will be accommodated in the system.

b) System Design Phase:

This is actually a multistep process. In this we tried to focus on some distinct attributes of a program like data structure, software architecture, interface representations and algorithmic detail. In this we tried to translate requirements into representation of the software which can be assessed for quality before coding begins. In the verifications, I have tried to ensure that the design is satisfying the

requirements and is of good quality. I have tried to find out if there is any misinterpretation of specified any requirements.

c) Code Generation Phase:

In this phase, we translated design of a system into code which can be compiled and executed. In this phase we have done actual coding for all forms. In this we tried to produce simple program which are clear to understanding and modify.

We have used dynamic method to verify the code. We have executed program on some test data and output of the program examined to determine if there are any error present. I have read the code carefully to detect any discrepancies between the design specification and the actual implementation.

d) Testing :

Testing plays a critical role in quality assurance for software. Due to limitations of the verification methods for the previous phase, design and requirement faults also appear in the code. Testing is used to detect these errors, in addition to the errors introduced during the coding phase.

HARDWARE AND SOFTWARE REQUIREMENTS:

In the proposed system we have used:

HARDWARE

Processor	X86 processor with 2.7 GHz
RAM	512 MB or more
Hard Disk	50 GB or more
Monitor	VGA/SVGA

SOFTWARE

Front-end	C#
Back-end	SQL Server 2008
O.S	Windows XP, Vista, 7, 8

➤ **FEASIBILITY STUDY :-**

A feasibility study is conducted to select the best system. That meets performance requirement. A system required performance is defined by a statement of constraints the identification of specific system objectives & a description of outputs. All projects are feasible-given unlimited time.

- ❖ All projects are feasible-given unlimited time.
- ❖ Feasibility and risks analysis are related in many ways, if project risk is great the Feasibility of providing quality software is reduced.

➤ **ECONOMICAL ANALYSIS :-**

A system is expected to provide benefits. Identification of each benefit and assignment of monetary value to it is required for cost benefit analysis. Benefits can be tangible and intangible, direct or indirect. As assessment of the economic justification for a computer based system project is cost benefit. Cost benefit analysis is complicated by criteria that vary with the characteristics of the system to be developed, the relative size of the project and the respected return on investment derived as part of the strategic plan.

➤ **TECHNICAL ANALYSIS :-**

During the technical analysis the analyst evaluates the technical merits of the system concept, at the same time collecting additional information about performance, reliability and maintainability. In some cases, this step also includes

the limited amount of research and design. Technical analysis begins with an assessment of the technical ability of the proposed system.

- ❖ Technically this project is very sophisticated and has faster execution comparatively used in project.
- ❖ During the technical analysis the analyst evaluates the technical merits of the system concept, at the same time collecting additional information about performance, reliability and maintainability. In some cases, this step also includes the limited amount of research and design.
- ❖ Technical analysis begins with an assessment of the technical ability of the proposed system.
- ❖ The tools available for technical analysis are derived from mathematical modelling, probability and statistic, queuing theory and control theory.

➤ **BEHAVIOURAL ANALYSIS:-**

Behavioural analysis is an operational principle for all requirements analysis methods. An estimate should be made of how strong a reaction the user is likely to have towards the development of a system. Behavioural analysis is an operational principle for all requirements analysis methods. The state-transition diagram represents the behaviour of a system by depicting its status and the events that use the system to change state.

➤ **SOCIAL FEASIBILITY :-**

Social feasibility is to determine of whether a proposed project will be acceptable to the people or not. Technically this project is feasible, for managing the proposal details as we are using .NET framework 3.5 which is available and it is very flexible which gives full control to designer. Economically also this project is very useful. As it is going to reduce marketing and other related cost.

This project is also operationally feasible, because it can be implemented easily. To implement this, only a compatible browser needs to be installed.

Proposed project is socially feasible because it gives user many options as well as it will be easy to handle

TECHNOLOGY

➤ MICROSOFT .NET FRAMEWORK :-

The **.NET Framework** (pronounced *dot net*) is a software framework developed by Microsoft that runs primarily on Microsoft Windows. It includes a large library and provides language interoperability (each language can use code written in other languages) across several programming languages. Programs written for the .NET Framework execute in a software environment (as contrasted to hardware environment), known as the Common Language Runtime (CLR), an application virtual machine that provides services such as security, memory management, and exception handling. The class library and the CLR together constitute the .NET Framework.

❖ Features:

- Interoperability:

Because computer systems commonly require interaction between newer and older applications, the .NET Framework provides means to access functionality implemented in newer and older programs that execute outside the .NET environment.

- Common Language Runtime engine:

The Common Language Runtime (CLR) serves as the execution engine of the .NET Framework. All .NET programs execute under the supervision of the CLR, guaranteeing certain properties and behaviors in the areas of memory management, security, and exception handling.

- Language independence:

The .NET Framework introduces a Common Type System, or CTS. The CTS specification defines all possible data types and programming constructs supported by the CLR and how they may or may not interact with each other conforming to the Common Language Infrastructure (CLI) specification.

- Simplified deployment:

The .NET Framework includes design features and tools which help manage the installation of computer software to ensure it does not interfere with previously installed software, and it conforms to security requirements.

- Security:

The design addresses some of the vulnerabilities, such as buffer overflows, which have been exploited by malicious software. Additionally, .NET provides a common security model for all applications.

➤ C#:-

C# is a multi-paradigm programming language encompassing strong typing, imperative, declarative, functional, generic, object-oriented (class-based), and component-oriented programming disciplines. It was developed by Microsoft within its .NET initiative and later approved as a standard by Ecma (ECMA-334) and ISO (ISO/IEC 23270:2006).

C# is one of the programming languages designed for the Common Language Infrastructure. C# is built on the syntax and semantics of C++, allowing C programmers to take advantage of .NET and the common language runtime.

C# is intended to be a simple, modern, general-purpose, object-oriented programming language. Its development team is led by Anders Hejlsberg.

❖ Features

- Output Cache extensibility:

Output caching, or Page-Level Caching, caches the entire rendered markup of an ASP.NET web page for a specific time-period. This has always been one of the essential features for ASP.NET that is used extensively to increase application performance.

- Session State compression:

The ASP.NET session state is a mechanism to maintain session-specific data through subsequent requests. With this compression feature, developers

can often reduce the time it takes for a web application to respond by reducing the size of session data.

- *View State mode for Individual Controls:*

View state is a mechanism to maintain page controls' state on subsequent post backs. ASP.NET stores the view state data for controls that are in the page.

ASP.NET has many advantages over other platforms when it comes to creating Web applications. Probably the most significant advantage is its integration with the Windows server and programming tools. Web applications created with ASP.NET are easier to create, debug, and deploy because those tasks can all be performed within a single development environment—Visual Studio .NET.

ASP.NET delivers the following other advantages to Web application developers:

- Executable portions of a Web application compiled so they execute more quickly than interpreted scripts.
- Use of the widely known Visual Basic programming language, which has been enhanced to fully support object-oriented programming.
- Introduction of the new Visual C# programming language, which provides a type-safe, object-oriented version of the C programming language.
- Automatic state management for controls on a Web page (called server controls) so that they behave much more like Windows controls
- The ability to create new, customized server controls from existing controls.

- Built-in security through the Windows server or through other authentication/authorization methods.
- Integration with Microsoft ADO.NET to provide database access and database design tools from within Visual Studio .NET.

➤ **MS-SQL 2008:-**

SQL Server 2008 (formerly codenamed "Katmai") was released on August 6, 2008 and aims to make data management self-tuning, self organizing, and self maintaining with the development of *SQL Server Always On* technologies, to provide near-zero downtime. SQL Server 2008 also includes support for structured and semi-structured data, including digital media formats for pictures, audio, video and other multimedia data. In current versions, such multimedia data can be stored as BLOBs (binary large objects), but they are generic bit streams. Intrinsic awareness of multimedia data will allow specialized functions to be performed on them. According to Paul Flossier, senior Vice President, Server Applications, Microsoft Corp., SQL Server 2008 can be a data storage backend for *different varieties of data: XML, email, time/calendar, file, document, spatial, etc* as well as perform *search, query, analysis, sharing, and synchronization* across all data types.

Other new data types include specialized date and time types and a *spatial* data type for location-dependent data. Better support for unstructured and semi-structured data is provided using the new *FILESTREAM* data type, which can be used to reference any file stored on the file system. Structured data and metadata about the file is stored in SQL Server database, whereas the

unstructured component is stored in the file system. Such files can be accessed both via Win32 file handling APIs as well as via SQL Server using T-SQL; doing the latter accesses the file data as a BLOB. Backing up and restoring the database backs up or restores the referenced files as well. SQL Server 2008 also natively supports hierarchical data, and includes T-SQL constructs to directly deal with them, without using recursive queries.

The Full-text search functionality has been integrated with the database engine. According to a Microsoft technical article, this simplifies management and improves performance.

Spatial data will be stored in two types. A "Flat Earth" (GEOMETRY or planar) data type represents geospatial data which has been projected from its native, spherical, coordinate system into a plane. A "Round Earth" data type (GEOGRAPHY) uses an ellipsoidal model in which the Earth is defined as a single continuous entity which does not suffer from the singularities such as the international dateline, poles, or map projection zone "edges". Approximately 70 methods are available to represent spatial operations for the Open Geospatial Consortium Simple Features for SQL, Version 1.1.

SQL Server includes better compression features, which also helps in improving scalability it enhanced the indexing algorithms and introduced the notion of filtered indexes. It also includes *Resource Governor* that allows reserving resources for certain users or window

Some Features:

- Fast Recovery.
- Includes Visual Studio Integration.
- Online Restore.
- Having Dedicated Administrator Connection.
- Stored Procedures are available for reusing the procedure in the system or in projects.

DESIGNS

➤ **SYSTEM PLANNING PER CHART:-**

➤ **GANTT CHART:-**

A Gantt chart is a horizontal bar chart used in project management as a tool for graphically representing the schedule of a set of specific activities or tasks.

The horizontal bars indicate the length of time allocated to each activity, so the x-axis of a Gantt chart is subdivided into equal units of time, e. g. days, weeks, and months.

The y-axis of a Gantt chart, on the other hand, simply lists all the activities or tasks being monitored by the Gantt chart. A simple look at a Gantt chart should enable its user to determine which tasks take the longest time to complete, which tasks are overlapping with each other, etc.

A Gantt chart indicates the following:

- 1) Durations and timelines of the listed activities;
- 2) The target and actual completion dates of the activities;
- 3) The cost of each activity;
- 4) The person or group of person responsible for each activity;
- 5) Milestones in the progress of the project.

Symbols used:

Since a Gantt chart is a graphical tool, it employs symbols to represent variety of information about a project. These symbols include:

- 1) The task bar, which is the horizontal bar used to indicate the duration of each activity in the Gantt chart;
- 2) The milestone marker, which denotes a major turning point in the project such as the release of an approved budget or the launching of a new product;
- 3) The link line, which shows the relationship between two tasks, such as the fact that one activity can only begin after another one is completed.

Gantt Chart:

DATA TABLE

1) Table Name: tbl_Patient

FIELD	SIZE	TYPE	DESCRIPTION
Patient_ID	50	varchar(50)	Patient ID
Patient_Name	50	varchar(50)	Patient Name
Patient_Age	50	varchar(50)	Patient Age
Patient_Gender	50	varchar(50)	Gender
Patient_Address		varchar(MAX)	Patient Address
Patient_Contact	50	varchar(50)	Contact Number
Patient_BloodGroup	50	varchar(50)	Patient's Blood Group
Patient_DOB		smalldatetime	Date of Birth
Patient_HealthProblem		varchar(MAX)	Health Problem

2) Table Name: tbl_Login

FIELD	SIZE	TYPE	DESCRIPTION
Username	50	varchar(50)	Username
Password	50	varchar(50)	Password
Role	50	varchar(50)	Role(Admin/User)

3) Table Name: tbl_Doctor

FIELD	SIZE	TYPE	DESCRIPTION
Doctor_ID	50	varchar(50)	Doctor's ID
Doctor_Name	50	varchar(50)	Doctor's Name
Doctor_Age	50	varchar(50)	Doctor's Age
Doctor_Gender	50	varchar(50)	Gender
Doctor_Address		varchar(MAX)	Doctor's Address
Doctor_Contact	50	varchar(50)	Doctor's Contact
Doctor_BloodGroup	50	varchar(50)	Doctor's Blood Group
Doctor_Speciality	50	varchar(50)	Doctor's Specialty
Doctor_DOB		smalldatetime	Date of Birth

4) Table Name: tbl_Bill

FIELD	SIZE	TYPE	DESCRIPTION
Bill_ID	50	varchar(50)	Bill ID
Doctor_ID	50	varchar(50)	Doctor's ID
Doctor_Name	50	varchar(50)	Doctors Name
Bill_Date		smalldatetime	Date
Patient_ID	50	varchar(50)	Patient's ID
Patient_Name	50	varchar(50)	Patient's Name
Bill_Total	50	varchar(50)	Total Amount

5) Table Name: tbl_BillDetails

FIELD	SIZE	TYPE	DESCRIPTION
Bill_ID	50	varchar(50)	Bill ID
Bill_Service	50	varchar(50)	Service Name
Bill_Amount	50	varchar(50)	Amount

6) Table Name: purchases

FIELD	SIZE	TYPE	DESCRIPTION
Purchase_ID	50	varchar(50)	Purchase ID
Purchase_Date		smalldatetime	Date
Purchase_Supplier	50	varchar(50)	Supplier Name
Purchase_Product	50	varchar(50)	Product Name
Purchase_Quantity	50	varchar(50)	Quantity
Purchase_Rate	50	varchar(50)	Rate
Purchase_Amount	50	varchar(50)	Total Amount

7) Table Name: tbl_Services

FIELD	SIZE	TYPE	DESCRIPTION
Service_ID	50	varchar(50)	Service ID

Service_Name	50	varchar(50)	Service Name
Service_Amount	50	varchar(50)	Amount to be Charged

8) Table Name: tbl_Product

FIELD	SIZE	TYPE	DESCRIPTION
Product_ID	50	varchar(50)	Product ID
Product_Name	50	varchar(50)	Product Name
Product_Amount	50	varchar(50)	Amount

9) Table Name: tbl_Appointment

FIELD	SIZE	TYPE	DESCRIPTION
Appointment_ID	50	varchar(50)	Appointment ID
Patient_ID	50	varchar(50)	Patient ID
Patient_Name	50	varchar(50)	Patient's Name
Appointment_Date		smalldatetime	Date of Appointment
Appointment_Time	50	varchar(50)	Timing of Appointment
Appointment_Service	50	varchar(50)	Service Name
Appointment_Doctor	50	varchar(50)	Doctor Name

Detailed life cycle of the project

ENTITY RELATIONSHIP DIAGRAM:-

EVENT TABLE:

<i>No.</i>	<i>EVENTS</i>	<i>TRIGGER</i>	<i>SOURCE</i>	<i>ACTIVITY</i>	<i>RESPONCE</i>	<i>DESTINATION</i>
1	Patient checks doctors availability	Doctors enquiry	Patient	Look for doctors availability	Doctors availability details	Patient
2	Patient takes test with doctor	Checking doctors availability	Patient	Look for the doctors	Test granted or not details	Patient
3	Patient cancel an Test	Test cancellation	Patient	Cancelation of Test	Test canceled	Patient
4	Changing an Test	Changing Test	Patient	Updating Test	Test changed	Patient
5	Admission of new patient	Patient's registration	Patient	Giving Admission	Patient Admitted	Receptionist, DCS
6	Updating patient's record	Change in patient details	DC	Updating patient's record	Patient's record updated	Receptionist, DCS
7	Deletion of patient's record	Patient record deletion	DC	Deleting patient's record	Patient's record deleted	Receptionist, DCS
8	Patient wants to do a particular test	New test for patient	Patient	Add new test details	Test details added	Receptionist, DCS
9	Discharging patient		DC	Creating bill	Bill generated Patient discharged	Patient, DC
10	Adding new doctor's details	Doctor's registration	DC	Adding new doctor's details	Doctor is hired	Receptionist, DCS

<i>No.</i>	<i>EVENTS</i>	<i>TRIGGER</i>	<i>SOURCE</i>	<i>ACTIVITY</i>	<i>RESPONCE</i>	<i>DESTINATION</i>
11	Updating doctor's record	Change in doctor details	DC	Updating doctor's record	Doctor's record updated	Receptionist, DCS
12	Deletion of doctor's record	Doctor's record deletion	DC	Deleting doctor's record	Doctor's record deleted	Receptionist, DCS
13	Adding new staff	Staff's registration	DC	Adding new registration	New registration added	Receptionist, DCS
14	Updating staff's record	Change in staff details	DC	Updating staff's record	staff's record updated	Receptionist, DCS
15	Deletion of staff's record	Staff's record deletion	DC	Deleting staff's record	Staff's record deleted	Receptionist, DCS
16	Adding new patient's operation	New patient's operation	DC	Adding new patient's operation	New patient's operation added	Receptionist, DCS
17	Adding new patient's Treatment	New patient's Treatment	DC	Adding new patient's Treatment	New patient's Treatment added	Receptionist, DCS

➤ **DATA FLOW DIAGRAM**

Meaning	Symbol	Description
Dataflow		A data flow shows the flow of information from its source to its Destination. A data flow is represented by a line, with arrowheads showing the Direction of flow.
Process		A process shows a transformation or manipulation of data Flows within the system.
External Entity		An external entity is source or destination of a data flow which is outside the area of Study.
Data store		It represent an entity(A place where data can be stored)

DFD:-

UML DIAGRAM

ACTIVITY DIAGRAM

USE CASE DIAGRAM

CLASS DIAGRAM

TESTING

TESTING:-

Testing is the most vital phase in completing a project. Testing mainly aims at checking the modularity, data flow and code thereby scrutinizing the intricacies of the system being developed.

A thorough testing has been carried out for this website. At all the required places appropriate validation has been done. User involvement at every stage has been propounded in the system. Testing is the crucial part of the system development to assure quality of the services, design and coding.

➤ TESTING OBJECTIVES:

Testing objective is the guideline that helps in carrying out proper testing of the system. The guidelines stated below are followed to carry out proper testing on the system. Testing is the process of executing a program with a goal to uncover the errors within the system. A successful test needs to be carried out in order to find undetected errors.

The main objective is to design the tests that systematically uncover different types of errors with minimum amount of time and errors. Testing demonstrates that the system functions appear to be working in a proper manner and that the performance requirements are met.

➤ **FORMAL TECHNICAL REVIEW:**

A formal technical review is a form of a peer review in which a team of qualified personnel examines the suitability of the software product for its intended use and identifies discrepancies from specifications and standards. The purpose of technical reviews is to arrive at a technically superior version of the product reviewed, by correction of defects.

There are various responsibilities assigned to the team members regarding the project.

- ❖ User participation is important for performing administrative tasks relative to the review, ensuring orderly conduct and ensuring that the reviews meet its objectives.

- ❖ One of the team members documents anomalies, action items, decisions and recommendations made by the review team.

- ❖ Technical experts are the active participants in the review and evaluation of the software product.

TEST PLAN:-

Test plan provides a road map for instituting software testing. This describes the overall testing strategy and the project management issues that are required to properly execute effective tests. Testing plan contains various test phases, start and end dates for each phase is described.

Testing is the process of analyzing a software item to detect the differences between existing and required conditions and to evaluate the features of the software item. Software Test Plan (STP) is designed to prescribe the scope, approach, resource and schedule of all testing activities.

The plan must identify the items to be tested, the features to be tested, the types of testing to be performed, the personnel responsibilities for testing, the resources and schedule required to complete testing, and the risks associated with the test plan.

TESTING METHODOLOGY:-

❖ **Blackbox testing:**

The first type of testing was at user level where all the applications were tested for the users.

❖ **WhiteBox Testing:**

The second level of testing was at functional level where each module of all the applications was tested. This testing continued throughout the entire project, evolving from component level (or unit) testing to integration testing.

❖ **Unit Testing:**

This testing focuses effort on the smallest part of software design-the module or software component. After the code has been developed, reviewed and verified for correspondence to component level design, unit testing case design begins.

❖ **Integration Testing:**

Unit testing ensures that all the modules are working fine independently but now we have to test the system as a whole; we have to develop a strategy, which sees that the system is functioning properly as a whole system.

Integration testing is systematic testing for constructing the program structure while at the same time conducting tests to uncover errors associated with interfacing. We will use bottom up integration testing where we will integrate the modules by starting with the lower individual modules and moving upward through the control hierarchy.

➤ **MODULES TO BE TESTED:**

- ❖ Login Module
- ❖ Registration Module

Modules:

➤ Log-In Module:

Test case No.	Test Case	Expected Result	Actual Result
1	Check for valid Username and Password.	User will be authenticated successfully	User authenticated successfully
2	Check for invalid Username and Password.	Alert 'Invalid Username and Password' will be displayed	Alert 'Invalid Username and Password' is displayed

➤ **Registration Module :**

Test case No.	Test Case	Expected Result	Actual Result
1	Check for only characters.	User will be authenticated successfully	User authenticated successfully
2	Check for numeric.	Alert 'Invalid Username and Password' will be displayed	Alert 'Invalid Username and Password' is displayed

SCREENSHOTS

1) Login:

2) Registration:

3) Home:

4) Add Patient :-

5) Update Patient :-

The screenshot displays a web-based application interface for a dental clinic. At the top, a navigation menu includes 'Patient', 'Doctor', 'Appointment', 'Services', 'Product', 'Purchases', 'Bill', 'Reports', and 'Logout'. The main content area features a 'Patient' form window with the following data:

Field	Value
Patient ID	1
Name	sharayu
Age	26
Gender	Female
Address	nerul
Contact No.	9879878767
Blood Group	B+
Date of Birth	10/10/1986
Health Problems	Root Canal

At the bottom of the form, there are three buttons: 'UPDATE', 'DELETE', and 'EXIT'. A cartoon tooth icon is positioned to the right of the form fields. The background of the application window shows a dental office with a desk, chair, and cabinets. The system tray at the bottom right indicates the time as 12:35 and the date as 03/06/2012.

6) Add Doctor :-

The screenshot displays a Windows desktop environment with a dental management software application open. The application's main menu includes 'Patient', 'Doctor', 'Appointment', 'Services', 'Product', 'Purchases', 'Bill', 'Reports', and 'Logout'. A 'Doctor' dialog box is centered on the screen, containing the following data:

Field	Value
Doctor ID	1
Name	kalpesh
Age	42
Gender	Male
Address	ghatkopar
Contact No.	676876876
Date of Birth	10/10/1970
Speciality	BDS
Blood Group	A+

At the bottom of the dialog box, there are three buttons: 'SAVE', 'CLEAR', and 'EXIT'. A 3D rendering of a tooth is positioned to the right of the form fields. The desktop background is a photograph of a dental clinic, and the taskbar on the right shows various application icons and the system clock displaying 12:36 on 03/06/2012.

Status

7) Update Doctor :-

The screenshot displays a web-based application for a dental clinic. The main menu at the top includes: Patient, Doctor, Appointment, Services, Product, Purchases, Bill, Reports, and Logout. The background image shows a modern dental office with purple walls, white cabinets, and a dental chair. A central window titled "Doctor" is open, containing the following data:

Doctor	
Doctor ID	1
Name	kalpesh
Age	42
Gender	Male
Address	ghatkopar
Contact No.	676876876
Date of Birth	10/10/1970
Speciality	BDS
Blood Group	A+

At the bottom of the form are three buttons: UPDATE, DELETE, and EXIT. A tooth icon is positioned to the right of the form fields. The system tray at the bottom right shows the time as 12:37 and the date as 03/06/2012.

Status

8) Add Appointment :-

The screenshot shows a web-based application for managing dental appointments. The main window is titled "Appointment" and contains a form with the following fields and controls:

- Appointment No.:** Text input field containing the value "1".
- Patient No.:** Text input field containing the value "1".
- Patient Name:** Text input field containing the value "sharayu".
- Appointment Date:** Date picker showing "03/06/2012".
- Appointment Time:** Time dropdown menu showing "10:30".
- Request Service:** Text input field containing the value "Root Cenal".
- Doctor Name:** Dropdown menu showing "kalpeeh".
- Search Patient:** A button located to the right of the Patient Name field.
- SAVE, CLEAR, EXIT:** Three buttons located at the bottom of the form.

The background of the application shows a dental clinic setting. The top navigation bar includes links for Patient, Doctor, Appointment, Services, Product, Purchases, Bill, Reports, and Logout. The system tray at the bottom right shows the time as 12:38 on 03/06/2012.

9) Update Appointment :-

The screenshot displays a web-based application for managing dental appointments. The main window is titled "Appointment" and features a blue tooth icon with a smile. The form contains the following fields and controls:

Appointment No.	<input type="text" value="1"/>	
Patient No.	<input type="text" value="1"/>	<input type="button" value="Search Patient"/>
Patient Name	<input type="text" value="sharayu"/>	
Appointment Date	<input type="text" value="06/03/2012"/>	
Appointment Time	<input type="text" value="11:00"/>	
Request Service	<input type="text" value="Root Canal"/>	
Doctor Name	<input type="text" value="kalpesh"/>	

At the bottom of the form, there are three buttons: **UPDATE**, **DELETE**, and **EXIT**. The background of the application shows a dental clinic setting with a desk and a chair.

Status

12:39
03/06/2012

10) Add/Update Services :-

Home

Patient Doctor Appointment Services Product Purchases Bill Reports Logout

Services

Serial No: 3

Service Name: Cleaning

Serial No: 2

Amount: 400

SAVE CLEAR UPDATE DELETE EXIT

Status

12:43
03/06/2012

11) Add/Update Product :-

12) Update Bill :-

The screenshot shows a web browser window with a navigation menu at the top: Patient, Doctor, Appointment, Services, Product, Purchases, Bill, Reports, Logout. The main content area features a large background image of a dental clinic. Overlaid on this is a window titled 'Bill' with a blue tooth logo and the word 'Bill' in a large font. The form contains the following fields and controls:

- Bill No: 1
- Doctor Name: kalpesh
- Date: 06/03/2012
- Patient Name: sharayu
- Service table:

Cleaning	400
Root Canek	2000
- Total: 2400
- Buttons: Update, Close, Delete

The desktop taskbar on the right shows icons for Home, My Computer, Google Chrome, and other applications. The system tray at the bottom right displays the time 12:51 and the date 03/06/2012. The word 'Status' is visible at the bottom left of the browser window.

CODING

1) Login:

```
using System;
using System.Collections.Generic;
using System.ComponentModel;
using System.Data;
using System.Drawing;
using System.Linq;
using System.Text;
using System.Windows.Forms;
using System.Data.SqlClient;

namespace SoftwareForDentalClinic
{
    public partial class frmLogin : Form
    {
        SqlConnection clsCon = new SqlConnection();
        SqlDataReader drRead;

        public frmLogin()
        {
            InitializeComponent();
        }
        public void clear()
        {
            txtUsername.Clear();
            txtPassword.Clear();
        }
        private void btnLogin_Click(object sender, EventArgs e)
        {
            try
            {
                //string str = txtUsername.Text;
                //string str1 = txtPassword.Text;
                drRead = clsCon.ReadData("select * from tbl_Login where
Username='" + txtUsername.Text + "' and Password='" + txtPassword.Text +
''''");
                if (drRead.HasRows)
                {
                    while (drRead.Read())
```

```

        {
            if (txtUsername.Text == drRead["Username"].ToString() &&
txtPassword.Text == drRead["Password"].ToString())
            {
                ConnectionString.pass = "success";

                //if (drRead["Role"].ToString() == "user")
                //{
                //    //Form f = new frmUserHome();
                //    //f.ShowDialog();
                //}
                //else
                //{
                //    //Form f = new frmHomePage();
                //    //f.ShowDialog();

                //}

```

```

Home f = new Home();
        f.ShowDialog();
        this.Hide();
    }
    else
    {
        ConnectionString.pass = "";
        MessageBox.Show("Incorrect Data !!!");
        txtUsername.Clear();
        txtPassword.Clear();
        txtUsername.Focus();
    }
}
else
{
    MessageBox.Show("Incorrect Data!!!");
    clear();
    txtUsername.Focus();
}
drRead.Close();
clsCon.con.Close();

```

```

    }
    catch (Exception ex)
    {
        MessageBox.Show(ex.Message);
        clsCon.con.Close();
    }
}

private void btnCancel_Click(object sender, EventArgs e)
{
    this.Close();
}

private void frmLogin_FormClosing(object sender,
FormClosingEventArgs e)
{
    if (ConnectionString.pass != "success")
    {
        Application.Exit();
    }
}

private void txtPassword_KeyDown(object sender, KeyEventArgs e)
{
    if (e.KeyCode == Keys.Enter)
    {
        btnLogin_Click(sender, e);
    }
}

private void button1_Click(object sender, EventArgs e)
{
    formregs f = new formregs();
    f.ShowDialog();
    this.Hide();
}

}
}
}

```

2) Registration:

```
using System.Data.SqlClient;

namespace SoftwareForDentalClinic
{
    public partial class formregs : Form
    {

        SqlConnection clsCon = new SqlConnection();
        SqlDataReader drRead;

        public formregs()
        {
            InitializeComponent();
        }

        private void button1_Click(object sender, EventArgs e)
        {
            if (txtname.Text != "" && textPword.Text != "")
            {
                clsCon.con.Close();
                clsCon.WriteData("insert into tbl_Login(Username,Password) values
(" + txtname.Text + ", " + textPword.Text + ")");
                MessageBox.Show("Record Inserted");
                txtname.Focus();

            }
            else
            {
                MessageBox.Show("Please Enter Details");
            }
        }

    }
}
```

3) Add Patient:

```
using System;
using System.Collections.Generic;
using System.ComponentModel;
using System.Data;
using System.Drawing;
using System.Linq;
using System.Text;
using System.Windows.Forms;
using System.Data.SqlClient;

namespace SoftwareForDentalClinic
{
    public partial class frmAddPatient : Form
    {
        SqlConnection clsCon = new SqlConnection();
        SqlDataReader drRead;

        int x;

        public frmAddPatient()
        {
            InitializeComponent();
        }
        public frmAddPatient(string sr_no)
        {
            InitializeComponent();
            txtPatientID.Text = sr_no;
        }

        private void frmAddPatient_Load(object sender, EventArgs e)
        {
            // for save

            if (txtPatientID.Text == "")
            {
```

```
btnUpdate.Visible = false;
btnDelete.Visible = false;
//lblUpdateClient.Visible = false;

try
{

    //clsCon.con.Open();
    increment();

}
catch (Exception ex)
{
    //MessageBox.Show(ex.Message);
    clsCon.con.Close();
}
finally
{
    clsCon.con.Close();
}

}

//for update

else
{
    try
    {

        btnSave.Visible = false;
        btnClear.Visible = false;
        //lblAddClient.Visible = false;

        clsCon.con.Close();
```

```

        drRead = clsCon.ReadData("select * from tbl_Patient where
Patient_ID='" + txtPatientID.Text + "'");

        while (drRead.Read())
        {

            txtName.Text = drRead["Patient_Name"].ToString();

            txtContact.Text = drRead["Patient_Contact"].ToString();
            //txtAge.Text = drRead["Patient_Age"].ToString();
            rtbProblem.Text = drRead["Patient_HealthProblem"].ToString();
            rtbAddress.Text = drRead["Patient_Address"].ToString();
            cboGender.Text = drRead["Patient_Gender"].ToString();
            cboBloodGroup.Text =
drRead["Patient_BloodGroup"].ToString();
            //dtpDOB.Text = drRead["Patient_DOB"].ToString();

        }
        drRead.Close();

    }
    catch (Exception ex)
    {
        MessageBox.Show(ex.Message);
    }
    finally
    {
        clsCon.con.Close();
    }
}
}
public void increment()
{

    //increment client ID

```

```

try
{
    clsCon.con.Close();
    drRead = clsCon.ReadData("select Patient_ID from tbl_Patient");
    if (drRead.HasRows)
    {
        while (drRead.Read())
        {
            x = Int32.Parse(drRead["Patient_ID"].ToString());
            x = x + 2;
        }
        drRead.Close();
    }
    else
    {
        x = 1;
    }
    txtPatientID.Text = x.ToString();
    clsCon.con.Close();
}
catch (Exception ex)
{
    MessageBox.Show(ex.Message);
    clsCon.con.Close();
}
}

public void clear()
{
    //Clear all data

    txtName.Clear();
    txtContact.Clear();
    //txtAge.Clear();
    cboBloodGroup.ResetText();
    cboGender.ResetText();
    rtbProblem.Clear();
}

```

```

        rtbAddress.Clear();
        //dtpDOB.ResetText();
    }

    private void btnSave_Click(object sender, EventArgs e)
    {
        if (txtName.Text != "" && rtbAddress.Text != "")
        {
            clsCon.con.Close();
            clsCon.WriteData("insert into
tbl_Patient(Patient_ID,Patient_Name,Patient_Age,Patient_Gender,Patient_Add
ress,Patient_Contact,Patient_BloodGroup,Patient_HealthProblem) values (" +
txtPatientID.Text + " , " + txtName.Text + " , " + comboBox1.Text + " , " +
cboGender.Text + " , " + rtbAddress.Text + " , " + txtContact.Text + " , " +
cboBloodGroup.SelectedText.ToString() + " , " + rtbProblem + ")");
            clear();
            increment();

            txtName.Focus();
            //count++;
        }
        else
        {
            MessageBox.Show("Please Enter Details");
        }
    }

    private void btnClear_Click(object sender, EventArgs e)
    {
        clear();
    }

    private void btnUpdate_Click(object sender, EventArgs e)
    {
        try
        {

            clsCon.con.Open();

```

```
        SqlCommand cmd = new SqlCommand("update tbl_Patient set
Patient_Name='" + txtName.Text + "',Patient_Age='" + comboBox1.Text +
"',Patient_Gender='" + cboGender.Text + "',Patient_Address='" +
rtbAddress.Text + "',Patient_Contact='" + txtContact.Text +
"',Patient_BloodGroup='" + cboBloodGroup.Text +
"',Patient_HealthProblem='" + rtbProblem.Text + "' where Patient_ID='" +
txtPatientID.Text + "' ", clsCon.con);
```

```
        cmd.ExecuteNonQuery();
        MessageBox.Show("Record Updated");
        // call clear function
        clear();
```

```
        this.Close();
```

```
    }
    catch (Exception ex)
    {
        MessageBox.Show(ex.Message);
    }
    finally
    {
        clsCon.con.Close();
    }
}
```

```
private void btnDelete_Click(object sender, EventArgs e)
{
    string message = "Are you sure want to delete this record?";
    string caption = " ";
    MessageBoxButtons buttons = MessageBoxButtons.YesNo;
    DialogResult result;
```

```
    result = MessageBox.Show(this, message, caption, buttons);
```

```
    try
    {
```

```

        if (result == DialogResult.Yes)
        {
            clsCon.con.Open();
            SqlCommand comm = new SqlCommand("Delete from tbl_Patient
where Patient_ID='" + txtPatientID.Text + "'", clsCon.con);

            //dataConnection.Open();

            comm.ExecuteNonQuery();

            MessageBox.Show("RECORD DELETED");

            //Clear();
        }

        else
        {
            btnExit.Focus();
        }
    }

    catch (Exception ex)
    {
        MessageBox.Show(ex.Message);
    }
    finally
    {
        clsCon.con.Close();
    }

    frmAddPatient fc = new frmAddPatient();
    fc.Activate();
    this.Close();
}

```

```

private void btnExit_Click(object sender, EventArgs e)
{
    this.Close();
}

private void txtContact_KeyPress(object sender, KeyPressEventArgs e)
{
    if ((e.KeyChar >= 48 && e.KeyChar <= 57) || e.KeyChar == 46 ||
e.KeyChar == 8 || e.KeyChar == 32 || e.KeyChar == 45 || e.KeyChar == 47 ||
e.KeyChar == 40 || e.KeyChar == 41 || e.KeyChar == 92)
        e.KeyChar = e.KeyChar;
    else
    {
        e.KeyChar = Convert.ToChar(0);
        MessageBox.Show("Please enter numeric values");
    }
}

private void panel1_Paint(object sender, PaintEventArgs e)
{
}

private void comboBox1_SelectedIndexChanged(object sender, EventArgs
e)
{
    for (int a = 1; a < 100; a++)
    {
        Console.WriteLine(comboBox1.Text[a]);
    }
}

private void txtPatientID_TextChanged(object sender, EventArgs e)
{
}
}
}

```

4) Add Doctor:

```
using System;
using System.Collections.Generic;
using System.ComponentModel;
using System.Data;
using System.Drawing;
using System.Linq;
using System.Text;
using System.Windows.Forms;
using System.Data.SqlClient;

namespace SoftwareForDentalClinic
{
    public partial class frmDoctor : Form
    {
        SqlConnection clsCon = new SqlConnection();
        SqlDataReader drRead;
        int x;

        public frmDoctor()
        {
            InitializeComponent();
        }
        public frmDoctor(string sr_no)
        {
            InitializeComponent();
            txtDoctorID.Text = sr_no;
        }

        private void frmDoctor_Load(object sender, EventArgs e)
        {
            // for save

            if (txtDoctorID.Text == "")
            {
                btnUpdate.Visible = false;
            }
        }
    }
}
```

```

btnDelete.Visible = false;
//lblUpdateClient.Visible = false;

try
{

    //clsCon.con.Open();
    increment();

}
catch (Exception ex)
{
    //MessageBox.Show(ex.Message);
    clsCon.con.Close();
}
finally
{
    clsCon.con.Close();
}

}

//for update

else
{
    try
    {

        btnSave.Visible = false;
        btnClear.Visible = false;
        //lblAddClient.Visible = false;

        clsCon.con.Close();
        drRead = clsCon.ReadData("select * from tbl_Doctor where
Doctor_ID='" + txtDoctorID.Text + "'");

```

```

while (drRead.Read())
{
    txtName.Text = drRead["Doctor_Name"].ToString();

    txtContact.Text = drRead["Doctor_Contact"].ToString();
    txtAge.Text = drRead["Doctor_Age"].ToString();
    txtSpeciality.Text = drRead["Doctor_Speciality"].ToString();
    rtbAddress.Text = drRead["Doctor_Address"].ToString();
    cboGender.Text = drRead["Doctor_Gender"].ToString();
    cboBloodGroup.Text =
drRead["Doctor_BloodGroup"].ToString();
    dtpDOB.Text = drRead["Doctor_DOB"].ToString();

}
drRead.Close();

}
catch (Exception ex)
{
    MessageBox.Show(ex.Message);
}
finally
{
    clsCon.con.Close();
}
}
}

public void increment()
{
    //increment client ID

    try

```

```

    {
        clsCon.con.Close();
        drRead = clsCon.ReadData("select Doctor_ID from tbl_Doctor");
        if (drRead.HasRows)
        {
            while (drRead.Read())
            {
                x = Int32.Parse(drRead["Doctor_ID"].ToString());
                x = x + 1;

            }
            drRead.Close();
        }
        else
        {
            x = 1;

        }
        txtDoctorID.Text = x.ToString();
        clsCon.con.Close();
    }
    catch (Exception ex)
    {
        MessageBox.Show(ex.Message);
        clsCon.con.Close();
    }
}

public void clear()
{
    //Clear all data

    txtName.Clear();
    txtContact.Clear();
    txtAge.Clear();
    cboBloodGroup.ResetText();
    cboGender.ResetText();
    txtSpeciality.Clear();

```

```

        rtbAddress.Clear();
        dtpDOB.ResetText();
    }

    private void btnSave_Click(object sender, EventArgs e)
    {
        if (txtName.Text != "" && rtbAddress.Text != "")
        {
            clsCon.con.Close();
            clsCon.WriteData("insert into
tbl_Doctor(Doctor_ID,Doctor_Name,Doctor_Age,Doctor_Gender,Doctor_Add
ress,Doctor_Contact,Doctor_BloodGroup,Doctor_DOB,Doctor_Speciality)
values (" + txtDoctorID.Text + "," + txtName.Text + ", " + txtAge.Text + ",
" + cboGender.Text + "," + rtbAddress.Text + "," + txtContact.Text + "," +
cboBloodGroup.Text + "," + dtpDOB.Value.ToString() + "," +
txtSpeciality.Text + ")");
            MessageBox.Show("Record Inserted");
            clear();
            increment();
            txtName.Focus();

        }
        else
        {
            MessageBox.Show("Please Enter Details");
        }
    }

    private void btnClear_Click(object sender, EventArgs e)
    {
        clear();
    }

    private void btnExit_Click(object sender, EventArgs e)
    {
        this.Close();
    }

    private void btnDelete_Click(object sender, EventArgs e)
    {

```

```
string message = "Are you sure want to delete this record?";
string caption = " ";
MessageBoxButtons buttons = MessageBoxButtons.YesNo;
DialogResult result;

result = MessageBox.Show(this, message, caption, buttons);

try
{
    if (result == DialogResult.Yes)
    {
        clsCon.con.Open();
        SqlCommand comm = new SqlCommand("Delete from tbl_Doctor
where Doctor_ID='" + txtDoctorID.Text + "'", clsCon.con);

        //dataConnection.Open();

        comm.ExecuteNonQuery();

        MessageBox.Show("RECORD DELETED");

        //Clear();

    }

    else
    {
        btnExit.Focus();
    }
}
```

```

    }
    catch (Exception ex)
    {
        MessageBox.Show(ex.Message);
    }
    finally
    {
        clsCon.con.Close();
    }

    frmAddPatient fc = new frmAddPatient();
    fc.Activate();
    this.Close();
}

private void btnUpdate_Click(object sender, EventArgs e)
{
    try
    {

        clsCon.con.Open();
        SqlCommand cmd = new SqlCommand("update tbl_Doctor set
Doctor_Name='" + txtName.Text + "',Doctor_Age='" + txtAge.Text +
"',Doctor_Gender='" + cboGender.Text + "',Doctor_Address='" +
rtbAddress.Text + "',Doctor_Contact='" + txtContact.Text +
"',Doctor_BloodGroup='" + cboBloodGroup.Text + "',Doctor_DOB='" +
dtpDOB.Value.ToString() + "',Doctor_Speciality='" + txtSpeciality.Text + "'
where Doctor_ID='" + txtDoctorID.Text + "' ", clsCon.con);

        cmd.ExecuteNonQuery();
        MessageBox.Show("Record Updated");
        // call clear function
        clear();

        this.Close();
    }
}

```

```

        catch (Exception ex)
        {
            MessageBox.Show(ex.Message);
        }
        finally
        {
            clsCon.con.Close();
        }
    }

    private void txtContact_KeyPress(object sender, KeyPressEventArgs e)
    {
        if ((e.KeyChar >= 48 && e.KeyChar <= 57) || e.KeyChar == 46 ||
            e.KeyChar == 8 || e.KeyChar == 32 || e.KeyChar == 45 || e.KeyChar == 47 ||
            e.KeyChar == 40 || e.KeyChar == 41 || e.KeyChar == 92)
            e.KeyChar = e.KeyChar;
        else
        {
            e.KeyChar = Convert.ToChar(0);
            MessageBox.Show("Please enter numeric values");
        }
    }
}
}

```

CONCLUSION

CONCLUSION

Dental Management System is a system which is a first step to change the medical industry methodology of keeping the data of patients as well as the other important information. This system will help the users to manage the dental information and make sure that all the important data are able to be use in the future time.

This includes information for the future treatment, as well as to do research from the data that had been captured.

As this system will be used for the dental management, the dental industry will soon be a high standard industry, which all the process will be done through the computer and specified system.

I actually learnt what exactly coding is when I did this project inC# & SQL Server 2008. It was different from what you read in books. It was a great learning process.

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